

Article

On the use of NB-IoT over GEO satellite systems with time-packed optical feeder links for over-the-air firmware/software updates of machine-type terminals

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Academic Editor: Carles Gómez

Version June 4, 2021 submitted to Journal Not Specified

Abstract: The verticals of 5G, such as the automotive, smart grid and smart cities sectors, will bring lots of new sensors and IoT devices requiring Internet connectivity. Most of these machine-type terminals will be sparsely distributed, covering a very large geographical area and, from time to time, will have to update their software, firmware and/or other relevant data. Given this situation, one viable solution to implement the “Over-the-Air” update of these IoT terminals can be done with the aid of GEO satellite systems. However, due to the ultra-dense radio frequency reuse factor that contemporary High-Throughput Satellite (HTS) systems implement in the *access link* to serve the IoT terminals, the use of a time-packed Free Space Optical (FSO) link represents a practical solution to avoid the bottleneck that the satellite gateway experiences in the *feeder link*. The performance of both *Detect-and-Forward* and *Decode-and-Forward* relaying strategies are studied, assuming that the single-carrier M-PAM symbols that are transmitted on the optical feeder link are mapped into M-QAM symbols that modulate the multiple sub-carriers of the OFDM-based radio access link. In addition, the benefits of encapsulating the NB-IoT frames into DVB-S2(X) satellite frames is also analyzed in detail. The effects of the impairments introduced in both optical feeder and radio access links are characterized in detail, and the end-to-end error correction capabilities of the Modulation and Coding Schemes (MCS) defined in the contemporary releases of the NB-IoT and DVB-S2(X) standards are studied for different working regimes.

Keywords: NB-IoT; DVB-S2(X); High-Throughput Satellite; Optical Feeder Link; Over-the-air updates; Time-Packing; Decode-and-Forward; Scintillation; Beam-Wander; Convolutional Coding.

1. Introduction

In the forthcoming years, an increased data rate capacity will be needed to provide enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) and massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC) fueled, among other reasons, by the large demand of video transmissions and IoT communications that are foreseen in future vertical services [1]. Specifically, according to CISCO, it is expected that Machine-to-Machine (M2M) connections will reach 14.7 billions by 2023. Applications such as home automation, home security, video surveillance, connected white goods and tracking are expected to represent almost half of the total M2M connections by 2023 [2]. Furthermore, the M2M services that are experiencing fastest growth in these days are connected car applications, such as fleet management, in-vehicle entertainment, emergency calling, vehicle diagnostics and navigation, with a Compound Annual Growing Rate (CAGR) in the order of 30%. All these applications share the same requirement, known

31 as Over-The-Air (OTA) programming, to update the software (*e.g.*, maps for navigation), security keys
32 (*e.g.*, for cryptography in the IoT devices), among other firmware updates.

33 Lately, 3GPP has started its studies to analyze the feasibility of integrating satellite networks into
34 its mobile communications systems [3]. Therefore, until these studies are completed, OTA services
35 provided over satellites are based on proprietary solutions owned by the satellite operators. Regarding
36 the feeder links, the dominant State-of-Art (SoA) technology for implementing them nowadays is based
37 on multi-beam reflect arrays in the Ka/Ku radio frequency band [4], [5], using the DVB-S2 standard.
38 However, there are many satellites in different orbits allocated in the Ka/Ku bands, and limited
39 bandwidth is currently available for new deployments, specially for 5G networks and beyond [6]. Note
40 that 6G systems will have to support terminals with a mobility speed of up to 1000 km/h, a connectivity
41 density of 10^7 devices/km², and peak data rates in downlink of up to 1 Tera-bit-per-second (Tbps)
42 to name a few of its requirements [7],[8],[9]. This means that the capacity of a satellite feeder link
43 must be increased, in order to avoid possible bottlenecks. Non-terrestrial networks, and specially the
44 satellite ones, will have to play a key role in the next generation of mobile communication systems,
45 integrating airborne, terrestrial and satellite networks to support in-flight connectivity. Then, multiple
46 technologies, not only radio-based ones, must be used to face the constraints that are foreseen for 6G.

47 In practical terms, the growth of OTA applications that is expected in the near future implies
48 that the downlink channel (*i.e.*, from the base station to the IoT terminals) will have to be improved
49 to support the forecast data traffic demand. Furthermore, given that Machine-type terminals may be
50 sparsely deployed in large geographical areas, then the use of satellite network would be an excellent
51 option to enable reliable IoT connectivity in a global scale. Towards this regard, the advent of Very
52 High Throughput Satellite (VHTS) systems will allow to achieve a total network capacity of few
53 Tbps [10,11]. In line with this, satellite operators are starting to study the viability of deploying optical
54 feeder links for Beyond 5G applications in GEO [6], where primary research analyses have been
55 already conducted [12]. Also, recent experimental studies in single optical LEO-to-ground links have
56 been reported in [13]. Larger communication bandwidths and free access to spectrum are the key
57 points in favour of optical wireless communications. Unfortunately, both radio and optical wireless
58 communications suffer from channel impairments. Therefore, from a long-term perspective, hybrid
59 solutions combining both technologies should be implemented in the forthcoming generations of
60 satellite networks [14] to increase the capacity of the feeder link.

61 Regarding the potential techniques to increase the spectral efficiency of the optical feeder link,
62 *e.g.* beamforming [15], NOMA [16], frequency reuse [17], this paper resorts to the ones based on
63 the shrinking the transmitted pulses. The so-called Faster-Than-Nyquist or time-packed techniques.
64 Initially proposed by Mazo in the 70's [18], has been proposed as potential technique for increasing
65 the spectral efficiency of Beyond 5G systems [19]. From the satellite point of view, the possibility of
66 reducing the transmission time without augmenting the transmission bandwidth fits very well for
67 overcoming the drawbacks of the optical channel, which heavily depend on the atmospheric conditions
68 such as clouds [6]. By doing so, the link layer may adjust the transmission time of the frames without
69 reducing the number of symbols to transmit according to weather forecasts [20].

70 This paper focuses on using optical feeder links for GEO satellite networks. Since initial studies
71 about the introduction of satellites into the 3GPP landscape have focused on low-latency applications,
72 most of these satellite communication scenarios are dominated by the use of Low Earth Orbit (LEO)
73 satellite constellations [21]. However, due to the longer space-to-ground link distances of GEO satellites,
74 more spectral-efficient techniques should be introduced in their architectures. Furthermore, observing
75 the evolution that 3GPP standards have experienced in the past, first integrating vehicular and railway
76 networks into 5G [8] and then airborne and satellites into 6G [7], it is highly probable that at some point
77 in the future, extra-terrestrial communications will be also integrated into the 3GPP ecosystem. In this
78 latter scenario, GEO satellites are in a good position for relaying data from the Earth to the outer space,
79 as discussed in the Moonlight initiative from ESA [22]. Therefore, this paper studies the approach that
80 GEO satellites should use to forward the information that they receive from the satellite gateway [23].

81 In the “*ideal*” case of a GEO satellite that implements a fully regenerative payload, the optical
82 feeder link would be terminated in the satellite, and a robust modulation and coding scheme should be
83 selected to address the bit error bursts that the turbulent optical satellite wireless channel introduce [24].
84 In the transparent non-regenerative “*bent-pipe*” solutions, on the other hand, the instantaneous value of
85 the radio signal is used to modulate the intensity of the optical carrier of the feeder link Laser Diode (LD)
86 with the aid of an external Match-Zehnder Modulator (MZM) [25]. Moreover, if time-packing encoding
87 is applied on the real-valued electrical signal that is used to modulate the intensity of the LD beam, the
88 data throughput of the optical feeder link can be increased even further, without the necessity of using a
89 wider communication bandwidth. This effect is obtained by shrinking the separation between adjacent
90 transmitted pulses [26], mitigating part of the Inter-Symbol Interference (ISI) power that time-packing
91 introduces with the aid of a linear equalizer that is placed on-board the GEO satellite before symbol
92 detection [27]. It is important to highlight that the impact of the residual ISI, which remains in the
93 forward link after the GEO satellite relaying, can be further mitigated with the proper selection of the
94 Modulation and Coding Schemes (MCS) to communication with the NB-IoT terminal [28].

95 The forward link of a satellite system can be divided into two parts, namely: i) The optical
96 feeder link (uplink), from the ground station to the GEO satellite, and ii) the radio access link
97 (downlink), from the GEO satellite to the NB-IoT user terminals. Therefore, and in order to improve
98 the achievable throughput of the forward direction of communication of the GEO satellite system
99 under different working conditions, this paper studies three different relaying architectures, namely:
100 1) *Detect-and-Forward* (non-regenerative strategy), where the GEO satellite only detects the symbols
101 of the NB-IoT frames that modulate the intensity of the optical beam, and forwards them to the
102 NB-IoT devices after *M-PAM to M-QAM* mapping; 2) *Decode-and-Forward with NB-IoT* (regenerative
103 strategy), where the GEO satellite detects and decodes the symbols of the NB-IoT frames that are
104 transported on the optical feeder link, and forwards them to the IoT devices after the NB-IoT frame
105 regeneration for downlink radio transmission is over; 3) *Decode-and-Forward with NB-IoT/DVB-S2(X)*
106 (regenerative strategy), where the NB-IoT frames are encapsulated into DVB-S2(X) satellite frames
107 for uplink transmission and, in the GEO satellite, the DVB-S2(X) decoding is performed to recover
108 the NB-IoT frame that is then transmitted to the NB-IoT terminals. We note that the previously listed
109 relaying architectures are also applicable to LEO and Medium Earth Orbit (MEO) satellites. However,
110 to adapt the study presented in this paper from GEO satellites with fixed positions in the sky to
111 LEO/MEO satellites that change their position on the sky at different speeds, the modeling of the
112 optical channel and its link budget must be adapted accordingly, reducing the (distance-dependent)
113 path loss attenuation that is experienced at lower orbits but adding additional effect of the atmosphere
114 at low-elevation angles, as well as pointing errors that may be incurred when the satellite is moving.

115 The remaining part of this article has been structured as follows: Section 2 summarizes the key
116 concepts to model the MCS defined in the NB-IoT standard, the three proposed relaying architectures
117 using GEO satellites with optical feeder links (one non-regenerative and two regenerative), and the
118 details of the time-packing equalization and low-complexity Log Likelihood Ratio (LLR) computation
119 for soft decoding. Section 3 studies the effect of the turbulent atmosphere in the optical feeder link,
120 with emphasis on the beam wander and scintillation that is introduced in the uplink transmission.
121 Section 4 presents the simulation setup and the performance figures in terms of end-to-end Block Error
122 Rate (BLER) and throughput. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

123 2. System Model

124 This section summarizes the key technological concepts that are needed to model the link level
125 performance of the NB-IoT communication, as well as the different relaying architectures that could
126 be used on-board the GEO satellite to interface the optical wireless signal (feeder link) into the radio
127 wireless signal (access link) that is forwarded by the GEO satellite to the NB-IoT terminals.

Figure 1. Typologies of NB-IoT deployment, namely stand-alone, in-band and guard-band deployments. All these deployment configurations are compatible with the channelization that is used in contemporary mobile communication standards, such as GSM/2G (200 kHz channel) and LTE/4G (180 kHz Physical Resource Block).

128 2.1. NB-IoT signal format for the satellite forward link

129 NB-IoT has been developed by 3GPP to cope with the large demand on IoT connectivity that is
 130 foreseen by the designers of the future generations of mobile communication standards (*i.e.*, 5G and
 131 beyond). NB-IoT has been conceived to be deployed in three different configurations or typologies,
 132 which are compatible with the spectrum allocation (channelization) that is used in contemporary
 133 mobile communication standards such as GSM (2G) and LTE (4G). An overview of these deployment
 134 typologies, which are known as *stand-alone*, *in-band* and *guard-band*, can be appreciated in Fig. 1.

135 In the stand-alone deployment, the NB-IoT signal occupies the bandwidth that corresponds to one
 136 (or few) of the 200 kHz GSM radio channels of the 2G radio spectrum; note that this strategy is suitable
 137 for the re-farming process of the GSM bands. In the in-band deployment, the NB-IoT signal is placed
 138 on the radio spectrum that corresponds to one (or few) Physical Resource Blocks (PRB) of an LTE
 139 carrier, where each PRB spans over 180 kHz of bandwidth and it is formed by 12 sub-carriers of 15 kHz
 140 bandwidth each. Finally, in the third typology of deployment known as guard-band deployment, the
 141 NB-IoT signal is placed on the guard bands that are reserved to prevent adjacent-channel interference
 142 between LTE carriers. Note that these strategies of deployment do not imply any additional cost and
 143 time to enter in service, provided the operator owns a licence either in the 2G/4G radio bands.

144 According to 3GPP standardization, both NB-IoT uplink and downlink transmissions occupy a
 145 communication bandwidth of 180 kHz in the radio portion of the electromagnetic spectrum. Moreover,
 146 as the downlink of NB-IoT defines the technology to communicate from the base station (eNB) to the
 147 user terminal (IoT device), we focus on this direction of communication to design the radio frame
 148 that should be used in the forward link of the IoT satellite system. Specifically, the downlink of
 149 NB-IoT uses few 15 kHz sub-carriers, providing a sampling time unit of $T_s = 1/(15000 \times 2048)$ sec.,
 150 which is identical to the one used in the LTE standard. Similarly, the time slot duration in NB-IoT
 151 is $T_{\text{slot}} = 15360 \times T_s = 0.5$ ms [29]. Two consecutive NB-IoT time slots constitute a subframe, which
 152 spans 1 ms. Similarly to LTE, a group of 10 subframes with total duration $T_{\text{frame}} = 10 \times 2 \times T_s = 10$ ms
 153 constitutes a NB-IoT frame.

154 The NB-IoT standard enables to repeat the transmission of the same information (block data)
 155 up to 2048 times, in order to extend the coverage range and increase the reliability of the data
 156 communication [29]. However, the higher is the number of repetitions that are performed, the lower is
 157 the spectral efficiency of the data communication that takes place. The NB-IoT link selects the Transport
 158 Block Size (TBS) on MAC layer from a variety of sizes, which range from 2 bytes (16 bits) up to 317
 159 bytes (2536 bits) [30]. The number of Modulation and Coding Schemes (MCS) that NB-IoT supports

Figure 3. Block diagram of the GEO satellite forward link for the three relaying configurations under analysis: 1) Detect-and-Forward with NB-IoT (green blocks with solid edges); 2) Decode-and-Forward with NB-IoT (orange blocks with dotted edges); and 3) Detect-and-Forward with NB-IoT/DVB-S2(X) (blue blocks with dashed edges).

199 symbols in DVB-S2(X) frames. Specifically, this paper analyzes the throughput of the following satellite
 200 architectures, namely: i) Case 1: NB-IoT modulated symbols detected at the satellite and forwarded
 201 to the corresponding IoT terminal; ii) Case 2: NB-IoT frames decoded until the bit-level, re-encoded,
 202 re-mapped at the satellite, and re-sent to the IoT terminal; iii) Case 3: NB-IoT modulated symbols are
 203 encapsulated in DVB-S2(X) frames and re-sent to the IoT terminal (see Fig. 3 for more details).

204 2.2.1. Case 1: Detect-and-Forward relaying of NB-IoT frames

205 This strategy is similar to the one used in transparent (bent-pipe) satellite architectures, but with
 206 the difference that the NB-IoT amplitude-modulated symbols in the optical feeder link are time-packed.
 207 The Inter-Symbol Interference (ISI) that time-packing introduces is removed in the satellite (see Section
 208 2.3) and, after that, the 4-PAM modulated symbols of the NB-IoT signal are detected, remapped to
 209 QPSK symbols, OFDM modulated, and re-sent to the IoT terminal over the radio access link. Finally,
 210 the IoT terminal computes the LLRs of the QPSK symbols (see Section 2.4) and feeds them in the soft
 211 convolutional decoder to estimate the transmitted NB-IoT frames from the gateway (see Fig. 3).

Let $s_{\text{ntp}}[k]$ be the k -th NB-IoT modulated symbols, $g_{\text{tx}}(\cdot)$ the transmit pulse-shaping square-root raised-cosine filter, T_s the Nyquist symbol time of the NB-IoT signal, and δ the time-packing overlapping factor. Then, the time-packed signal that is generated by the gateway can be written as

$$s_{\text{tp}}(t) = \sum_k s_{\text{ntp}}[k] g_{\text{tx}}(t - k(1 - \delta)T_s). \quad (1)$$

Next, the Electrical-to-Optical (E/O) conversion of $s_{\text{tp}}(t)$ is done with a MZM driven by voltage

$$v_{\text{mzm}}(t) = V_B + \beta \tilde{s}_{\text{tp}}(t) (V_\pi / \pi), \quad (2)$$

where V_B and V_π are the bias and half-wavelength voltages of the MZM, β is the intensity modulation index (scaling factor) that is selected for the communication in the optical feeder link, and

$$\tilde{s}_{\text{tp}}(t) = s_{\text{tp}}(t) / \sqrt{\mathbb{E}\{|s_{\text{tp}}(t)|^2\}}, \quad (3)$$

212 where $\mathbb{E}\{\cdot\}$ is the mathematical expectation operator that determines the mean value of the signal.

After that, the time-packed signal is transmitted through the optical feeder link. At the satellite, the Optical-to-Electrical (O/E) conversion is performed with the aid of a Photodetector [28], obtaining

$$r_{\text{tp,sat}}[n] = \sqrt{\left(\frac{E_b}{N_0}\right)_{\text{fl}}} h_{\text{fl}} s_{\text{tp}}[n] + \eta_{\text{fl}}[n], \quad (4)$$

213 where h_{fl} is the equivalent channel gain of the optical feeder link (see Section 3), $s_{\text{tp}}[n]$ is the n -th
214 discrete sample of the time-packed signal in the gateway, and $\eta_{\text{fl}}[n]$ is the resulting noise signal of unit
215 power after the O/E conversion in the satellite (see Section 4.1). The value of $(E_b/N_0)_{\text{fl}}$ represents the
216 equivalent bit-to-noise-energy ratio of the optical feeder link.

The estimations of the non-time packed NB-IoT symbols at the satellite (*i.e.*, $\hat{s}_{\text{ntp,sat}}$) are obtained after the received signal samples in (4) are first matched-filtered and then equalized (see Section 2.3). Then, the 4-PAM non-time packed signals are re-mapped into QPSK symbols, OFDM modulated, and finally transmitted to the corresponding IoT device. Due to that, the k -th sample of the signal that the IoT device receives in the radio access link attains the form

$$r_{\text{ntp,iot}}[k] = \sqrt{\left(\frac{E_b}{N_0}\right)_{\text{al}}} h_{\text{al}} \hat{s}_{\text{ntp,sat}}[k] + \eta_{\text{al}}[k], \quad (5)$$

217 where $\eta_{\text{al}}[k]$ is the unit power noise signal, h_{al} is the gain of the radio access channel, and $(E_b/N_0)_{\text{al}}$ is
218 the bit-to-noise-energy ratio of the radio access link. Finally, the LLR of the received QPSK modulated
219 symbols are computed, and soft-decoding it is conducted to detect the transmitted bits from the
220 gateway, b_{gw} (See Fig. 3).

221 2.2.2. Case 2: Decode-and-Forward relaying of NB-IoT frames

222 Similar to *Case 1* (see Section 2.2.1), the optical receiver of the satellite removes the time-packed
223 interference (see Section 2.3) but, instead of remapping the 4-PAM modulation to QPSK directly, it
224 computes the LLRs of the 4-PAM modulation that are used by the soft-Viterbi decoder to detect the
225 message bits transmitted from the gateway (see Section 2.4). After that, the estimated message bits
226 $\hat{b}_{\text{gw,sat}}$ are re-encoded, QPSK mapped, OFDM modulated, and forwarded to the corresponding IoT
227 device. There, the NB-IoT receiver computes the LLRs of the receive QPSK symbols, to use them in the
228 soft-Viterbi algorithm to detect the transmitted bits from the gateway $\hat{b}_{\text{gw,iot}}$.

229 Let $\hat{s}_{\text{ntp,sat}}[n]$ be the estimated symbols of the non-time-packed 4-PAM modulated symbols at the
230 satellite. Then, the following step of *Case 2* consists in computing the two LLRs per modulated symbol
231 of the 4-PAM constellation, denoted as LLR_{b_0} and LLR_{b_1} (see Section 2.3). After that, the soft-Viterbi
232 decoder at the satellite estimates the original transmitted bits $\hat{b}_{\text{gw,sat}}$, re-encodes them to regenerate the
233 coded NB-IoT bits $c_{\text{ntp,sat}}$, map them to QPSK symbols $s_{\text{ntp,sat}}$, and follow as in *Case 1* (see Fig. 3).

234 2.2.3. Case 3: Detect-and-Forward relaying of NB-IoT frames encapsulated in DVB-S2(X)

235 The third case consists in encapsulating the NB-IoT encoded bits into DVB-S2(X) frames. Next,
236 the LDPC coded bits from DVB-S2(X) are 4-PAM modulated, pulse-shaped, time-packed, and sent to
237 the satellite. There, the time-packed interference is removed (see Section 2.3), and the LLRs for the
238 4-PAM modulation are computed and fed into the soft-LDPC decoder of the DVB-S2(X) [33]. After
239 that, the NB-IoT encoded bits are des-encapsulated from the DVB-S2(X) frames, mapped to QPSK

240 symbols, OFDM modulated, and forwarded to the IoT device. There, the LLRs of the QPSK symbols
 241 are first computed, and then used by its soft-Viterbi decoder to detect the message of the gateway.

242 Let $c_{\text{iot,gw}}$ be the NB-IoT convolutional encoded signal at the terrestrial gateway, which is
 243 encapsulated into the DVB-S2(X) frame. Due to the payload size of a NB-IoT and a DVB-S2(X) frame is
 244 different, several NB-IoT convolutional codewords can be packed together into the input message of
 245 the DVB-S2(X) physical layer frames. We recall that at the physical layer, a DVB-S2(X) frame is first
 246 BCH encoded and then LDPC encoded. The BCH encoding is used to remove the possible error floors
 247 of the LDPC decoding, which aims at compensating the impairments that introduce communication
 248 channel (*i.e.*, the optical feeder link in our case). Let us assume that $c_{\text{dvb,gw}}$ denotes the input frame to
 249 the DVB-S2(X) encoder at the gateway. Then, it can convey up to P NB-IoT convolutional coded frames
 250 as $c_{\text{dvb,gw}} = [c_{\text{iot,gw}}(0) \cdots c_{\text{iot,gw}}(P-1)]$. Next, the DVB-S2(X) coded frames are 4-PAM modulated,
 251 E/O converted, and sent to the satellite on the optical feeder link. At the satellite, the O/E conversion
 252 is carried out, and the received signal samples are matched-filtered and equalized to mitigate the ISI
 253 introduced by time-packing. Likewise *Case 2*, the two LLRs are computed per 4-PAM symbol, *i.e.*,
 254 LLR_{b_0} and LLR_{b_1} (see Section 2.3). However, in *Case 3* these LLRs are introduced into the soft LDPC
 255 decoder, not in the soft-Viterbi decoder as it was used in *Case 2*. After that, the NB-IoT encoded bits
 256 are des-encapsulated from the decoded DVB-S2(X) frames, QPSK mapped, OFDM modulated, and
 257 forwarded to the IoT terminal over the radio access link. Finally, at the IoT device, the processing for
 258 detecting the transmitted message is the same as the one that was explained for *Case 1*.

259 2.3. Equalization of the Time-Packed signal

260 The three proposed relaying architectures rely on time-packing signalling in the optical feeder
 261 link to increase the throughput even further. Unfortunately, the use of time-packing introduces ISI
 262 that must be mitigated in reception at the satellite. The optimal strategy for cancelling this unwanted
 263 ISI consist in resorting the Maximum-Likelihood Sequence Decoding (MLSD) [34], which can be
 264 implemented efficiently with the Viterbi algorithm [35]. However, to increase the throughput of the
 265 optical feeder link, it is necessary use a low roll-off factor and large overlapping factor, two things that
 266 increase notably the complexity of the Viterbi Algorithm to be implemented in the satellite [27]. Due to
 267 the impracticability of this solution, alternative strategies should be considered. Towards this regard, in
 268 this paper we use a two-side Least Mean Square (LMS) filter to equalize the time-packed channel. Thus,
 269 the equalization strategy consists of two steps: 1) Compute the weights of the interference canceller by
 270 means of a training sequence; 2) Apply the pre-computed weights to the received time-packed signal
 271 from the gateway. These weights have to be computed for each overlapping factor that can be used.

Let us assume that \mathbf{r} is the vector that stacks the received samples of the time-packed signal,
 $\mathbf{w} = [w[0] \cdots w[L-1]]^T$ is the vector of L weights in the LMS equalizer, and $\mathbf{y}[n]$ is the buffer that
 contains the received samples that participates in the equalization process of the n -th time-packed
 received symbol. Then, the equalization of the n -th transmitted symbol attains the form

$$z[n] = \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{y}, \quad \mathbf{y} = [r[n - (L-1)/2] \cdots r[n] \cdots r[n + (L-1)/2]]^T. \quad (6)$$

During the training process, the *ideal* values of the signal samples at the output of the equalizer
 $z[n]$ are known, enabling to determined the most convenient equalization weights. Specifically, the
 weights \mathbf{w} have been computed by using the LMS-algorithm strategy [26,36], *i.e.*,

$$\mathbf{w}[q] = \mathbf{w}[q-1] + \mu e[q] \mathbf{y}[q], \quad (7)$$

272 where $\mathbf{w}[p]$ contains the equalizer weights at the p -th training iteration, μ is the forgetting factor, and
 273 $e[p] = z_t[p] - z[p]$ is the error between the training symbol $z_t[p]$ and its estimation from (6).

Table 1. Closed-form expressions for the LLR_{b_0} and LLR_{b_1} of both 4-PAM and QPSK modulations.

LLR_{b_m}	4-PAM	QPSK
LLR_{b_0}	$4a \log \left(\frac{\cosh(a-b)}{\cosh(a+b)} \right)$	$\frac{2\text{Im}(x)}{\sigma_n^2}$
LLR_{b_1}	$-2b + \log \left(\frac{\cosh(c)}{\cosh(a)} \right)$	$\frac{2\text{Re}(x)}{\sigma_n^2}$

274 2.4. Computation of the LLRs for the 4-PAM and the QPSK modulation schemes

275 In this paper, the NB-IoT transmitted data is encoded with a convolutional coding scheme.
 276 Furthermore, for the *Case 3*, the encapsulated NB-IoT frames are protected using the LDPC code
 277 of the DVB-S2(X) standard. In both cases, soft-decoding is used and, due to that, the LLRs has
 278 to be determined. However, the IoT devices and the satellite node may be limited in their power
 279 consumption. Fortunately, for both modulation schemes used in this paper (*i.e.*, 4-PAM and QPSK), it
 280 is possible to derive reduced complexity closed-form formulas for computing the optimal LLRs.

The 4-PAM modulation scheme is used in the optical feeder link, whereas the QPSK modulation is used in the radio access link. We assume that Gray-mapping is used in both cases, and that their corresponding modulation symbols are $\mathbf{s}_{4\text{-pam}} = \{-3, -1, 1, 3\}/\sqrt{5}$ for 4-PAM and $\mathbf{s}_{\text{QPSK}} = \{-1-j, 1-j, 1+j, -1+j\}/\sqrt{2}$ for QPSK (see Fig. 4). Since both modulation schemes transport two bits per modulated symbol, it is necessary to compute two LLRs per modulated symbol. Thus, the closed-form expression for computing these LLRs is given by

$$LLR_{b_m} = -\log \left(\frac{\left(\sum_{p=0; s_p|b_m=0}^{M/2} e^{-\frac{|z-hs_p|^2}{2\sigma_n^2}} \right)}{\left(\sum_{q=0; s_q|b_m=1}^{M/2} e^{-\frac{|z-hs_q|^2}{2\sigma_n^2}} \right)} \right), \quad (8)$$

where LLR_{b_m} is the LLR that corresponds the m -th bit of the modulated symbol, σ_n^2 is the noise power, M is the number of constellation symbols, h is the communication channel, z is the received data at the input of the de-mapper, and s_p (s_q) symbolizes the constellation symbols in which the m -th bit is 0 (1). Thus, according to (8) and the Gray mapping proposed in Fig. 4, the LLR of the first bit b_0 for both 4-PAM and QPSK modulation schemes is given by

$$LLR_{b_0} = -\log \left(\frac{\left(e^{-\frac{|z-hs_0|^2}{2\sigma_n^2}} + e^{-\frac{|z-hs_1|^2}{2\sigma_n^2}} \right)}{\left(e^{-\frac{|z-hs_2|^2}{2\sigma_n^2}} + e^{-\frac{|z-hs_3|^2}{2\sigma_n^2}} \right)} \right), \quad (9)$$

whereas LLR of the second bit b_1 attains the form

$$LLR_{b_1} = -\log \left(\frac{\left(e^{-\frac{|z-hs_0|^2}{2\sigma_n^2}} + e^{-\frac{|z-hs_3|^2}{2\sigma_n^2}} \right)}{\left(e^{-\frac{|z-hs_1|^2}{2\sigma_n^2}} + e^{-\frac{|z-hs_2|^2}{2\sigma_n^2}} \right)} \right). \quad (10)$$

If (9) and (10) are computed for 4-PAM and QPSK modulation schemes, the closed-form expressions for LLR_{b_0} and LLR_{b_1} are shown in Table 1. In these closed-form formulas, we have that

$$a = (2zs_1)/(2\sigma_n^2), \quad b = (4s_1^2)/(2\sigma_n^2), \quad c = 3 \cdot a, \quad (11)$$

281 where s_1 is the second symbol of the 4-PAM constellation, *i.e.* $s_1 = -1/\sqrt{5}$ (See Fig. 4) and signal z
 282 represents the data after equalizing the time-packed signal (see Section 2.3). For *Case 2*, this signal
 283 z corresponds to the NB-IoT one, and its LLRs are introduced in the soft-convolutional decoder

284 for recovering the transmitted message to regenerate the NB-IoT signal. For *Case 3*, the signal z
 285 corresponds to the DVB-S2(X) after the time-packing equalization. The computed LLRs for this case is
 286 introduced to the LDPC decoder of DVB-S2(X) receiver [33]. After that, the encoded NB-IoT bits are
 287 QPSK mapped, OFDM modulated, and forwarded to the IoT-device. Finally, at the IoT receiver, the
 288 LLRs of the received QPSK modulation symbols are computed for all cases under study. These LLRs
 289 are used by the soft-Viterbi decoder to recover the message transmitted from the satellite gateway.

	00	01	11	10
	s_0	s_1	s_2	s_3
4-PAM	$-3/\sqrt{5}$	$-1/\sqrt{5}$	$1/\sqrt{5}$	$3/\sqrt{5}$
QPSK	$(-1-j)/\sqrt{2}$	$(1-j)/\sqrt{2}$	$(1+j)/\sqrt{2}$	$(-1+j)/\sqrt{2}$

Figure 4. Gray mapping between 4-PAM and QPSK symbols performed in the satellite node.

290 3. Optical Wireless Satellite Channel Model

291 The optical signal that is used to transport the data symbols from the satellite gateway to the GEO
 292 satellite must go through the different layers of the Earth's atmosphere. Unfortunately, the power
 293 loss that the optical feeder link experiences in the *uplink* direction of communication is larger than the
 294 one observed in *downlink*. This is because, in the ground-to-satellite communication, the optical signal
 295 starts to spread and accumulate distortion as soon as it leaves the satellite gateway transmitter.

296 3.1. Atmospheric power losses: Absorption and scattering modelling

The power loss of the optical feeder link is a function of the atmospheric attenuation, which depends on both absorption and scattering effects that the light signal experiences while propagating [37]. To compute this value, the atmospheric attenuation coefficient

$$\gamma_{\text{atm}} = \alpha_m + \alpha_a + \beta_m + \beta_a \quad (12)$$

297 needs to be computed, where α_m and α_a are the molecular and aerosol absorption coefficients,
 298 respectively, whereas β_m and β_a are the molecular and aerosol scattering coefficients, respectively.

299 **Modelling of absorption:** At Infrared (IR) wavelengths, the principal atmospheric absorbers are
 300 the molecules of water, carbon-dioxide, and ozone. As expected, the atmospheric absorption is a
 301 wavelength-dependent phenomenon. Therefore, the operating wavelength for optical feeder link
 302 transmissions should be chosen to minimize this loss, using the atmospheric transmission windows in
 303 which the molecular and aerosol absorption is less than 0.2 dB/km for clear sky conditions [38]. In
 304 addition to the low-absorption requirements, most optical feeder links are designed to work in the
 305 780-850 nm and 1520-1600 nm windows because there are *off-the-shelf* lasers and detectors commercial
 306 available to work in these wavelengths.

307 **Modelling of scattering:** Like absorption, scattering is also a phenomenon that is strongly dependent
 308 on the operating wavelength. If the size of the atmospheric particles is small in comparison to the
 309 optical feeder link wavelength, then *Rayleigh scattering* is produced. Particles like air molecules and
 310 haze cause Rayleigh scattering [39] and affect notably optical wireless transmissions in the Visible
 311 Light (VL) and Ultraviolet (UV) regions; on the other hand, Rayleigh scattering can be neglected for
 312 optical feeder link wavelengths in the IR range (*i.e.*, when $\lambda \gg 1 \mu\text{m}$). Similarly, when the atmospheric
 313 particles size is comparable with the operating wavelength, then *Mie scattering* is produced. Aerosol

314 particles, fog and haze are the major contributors of Mie scattering, and this phenomenon is dominant
 315 for wavelengths in the IR range. Finally, if the atmospheric particles are much larger than the operating
 316 wavelength, the scattering is better described by geometrical optical models, which should be used in
 317 case of rain, snow and hail weather conditions [40].

Modelling the transmittance of the Earth's atmosphere: Apart from the previously described λ -dependent effects, the specific value that the atmospheric attenuation coefficient takes depends on the concentration of molecules (and aerosols) of the Earth's atmosphere at different altitudes h . Based on this assumption, the atmospheric transmittance that an optical feeder link with zenith angle ζ experiences is given by

$$T_{\text{atm}}(\lambda) = \exp \left\{ -\sec(\zeta) \int_{h_0}^H \gamma(\lambda, h) dh \right\}, \quad (13)$$

318 where h_0 is the altitude of the satellite gateway (ground station) over the sea level, H is the vertical
 319 height at which the GEO satellite is placed, and $\gamma(\lambda, h)$ is the attenuation coefficient at wavelength λ
 320 and altitude h . Based on this formula, it is possible to see that atmospheric transmittance is increased at
 321 low zenith angles (*i.e.*, at high elevation angles), as the fraction of the incident electromagnetic power
 322 that is transferred through the atmosphere layers is increased.

323 **Power losses due to fog:** From the common weather conditions, fog is the one that contributes most
 324 in the absorption and scattering of the optical signal when propagates through the Earth's atmosphere.
 325 In presence of fog, the optical feeder link connectivity is put at risk seriously, particularly when the fog
 326 layer next to the ground station extends vertically very high, forming a fog layer that can be as thick as
 327 400 m over the Earth's surface. In such critical weather conditions, the use of very high power lasers
 328 (1550 nm) with special mitigation techniques is the only option to maximize the chances of optical
 329 feeder link connectivity. As an alternative method to the Mie scattering theory, the attenuation due to
 330 fog for different wavelengths can be estimated using empirical models that use as input parameter
 331 the visibility in km measured on the VL region (550 nm). For a comparison of the fog attenuation at
 332 different wavelengths (850 nm and 950 nm), please refer to [41]. Note that in extreme cases, where the
 333 visibility due to fog is reduced to about 50 m, atmospheric attenuation can be as high as 350 dB/km [42].

334 **Power losses due to rain:** The impact of rain in the propagation of optical signals is not as pronounced
 335 as fog, because the size of the rain droplets are significantly larger in size (from 100 μm to 1000 μm)
 336 when compared to operating wavelengths of optical feeder links. For example, the attenuation loss
 337 in light rain (2.5 mm/h) to heavy rain (25 mm/h) ranges from 1 dB/km to 10 dB/km for 850 nm
 338 and 1550 nm operating wavelengths, respectively [43]. Note that the low clouds, which are usually
 339 accompanying the rainy weather, are the source of strong attenuation in most optical feeder links.
 340 In order to combat the huge power loss that takes place in such conditions, it is recommended to
 341 include a few tens-of-dB margin (*e.g.*, 30 dB) when designing the link budget of the optical wireless link.
 342 Moreover, optical feeder link designers can also implement adaptive coding and modulation schemes
 343 to address the varying weather conditions in the geographical area around the ground station [26].

344 **Power losses due to snow:** Finally, since the size of snow droplets is between the size of rain and fog
 345 droplets, the atmospheric attenuation for dry/wet snow conditions is usually stronger than the one
 346 in presence of rain, but not as severe as the one in case of fog. However, during heavy snow storms,
 347 the path of the optical feeder link can be completely blocked for the presence of densely-packed snow
 348 flakes in the propagation path. In such cases, the attenuation is similar to the one observed in foggy
 349 weather (30-350 dB/km) and, as expected, can seriously put at risk the optical feeder link connectivity.

350 3.2. Atmospheric turbulence: Beam wander, Beam spreading, and Beam scintillation

351 Atmospheric turbulence is a random phenomenon that is caused by the variation of the
 352 temperature and pressure on the atmosphere layers that are in the propagation path of the optical
 353 wireless signal. These temperature and pressure inhomogeneities form turbulent cells, known as

354 *eddies*, which have different sizes and different diffractive indexes. The eddies act as if prisms/lenses
 355 were deployed in the propagation path, introducing constructive and destructive interference in the
 356 received optical signal. The perturbations that atmospheric turbulence introduces in the wave-front
 357 of the optical beam can be physically described by the Kolmogorov model [44]. Depending on
 358 the size of the turbulent eddies with respect to the transmitted beam size, three types of atmospheric
 359 turbulence-induced effects can be identified, namely: *Beam wander*, *beam spreading*, and *beam scintillation*.

360

361 **Turbulence-induced beam wander:** This phenomenon takes place when the size of the turbulent
 362 eddies is *larger* than the size of the optical beam. Beam wander results in a random deviation of the
 363 optical beam from its planned (rectilinear) propagating path and, in extreme displacement situations,
 364 may lead to the failure of the optical wireless link. Beam wander is a major concern in the uplink
 365 transmission of an optical feeder link, as the beam size in the ground-to-satellite transmission is often
 366 smaller than the size of the turbulent eddies, resulting in a beam displacement at the receiver side that
 367 can be as large as several hundred meters.

368 In case of a collimated beam (plane wave model), the Root Mean Square (RMS) displacement due
 369 to beam wander for an uplink path with zenith angle ζ can be written as

$$\sigma_{\text{BW}}^2 = 7.25 (H - h_0)^2 \sec^3(\zeta) W_0^{-1/3} \int_{h_0}^H C_n^2(h) \left(1 - \frac{h - h_0}{H - h_0}\right)^2 dh \quad (14)$$

$$\cong 0.54 (H - h_0)^2 \sec^2(\zeta) \left(\frac{\lambda}{2W_0}\right)^2 \left(\frac{2W_0}{r_0}\right)^{5/3}, \quad (15)$$

where H is the altitude of the GEO satellite (receiver), h_0 is the altitude of ground station (transmitter),
 W_0 is the initial beam size, and r_0 is the atmospheric coherence width, which is also known now as
Fried's coherence length, *Fried's parameter*, or simply coherence length [45]. The Fried's coherence length
 is a widely used descriptor of the level of atmospheric turbulence at a particular site and, for a known
 structure constant profile $C_n^2(h)$ and plane wave model (collimated beam), it is given by [46]

$$r_0 = \left[0.423 k^2 \sec(\zeta) \int_{h_0}^H C_n^2(h) dh\right]^{-3/5}, \quad (16)$$

370 where $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ is the wavenumber of the optical beam. As expected, $C_n^2(h)$ varies with the time of
 371 the day, the geographical location, and the altitude. Therefore, for vertical optical links (slant paths),
 372 the value of $C_n^2(h)$ has to be integrated over the complete propagation path, starting from the height
 373 of the ground station above the sea level and ending at the altitude in which the Earth's atmosphere
 374 vanishes (*i.e.*, at about 40 km).

Various empirical models for $C_n^2(h)$ have been proposed in the literature to estimate the
 turbulence profiles, using as reference the experimental measurements that were carried out at different
 geographical locations, time of the day, wind speed, terrain types, among others. The most widely
 used model to characterize the refractive index structure of the atmosphere for vertical links (slant
 paths) is the so-called Hufnagel-Valley (H-V) model [45], *i.e.*,

$$C_n^2(h) = A_0 \exp\left(-\frac{h}{100}\right) + 5.94 \times 10^{-53} \left(\frac{v}{27}\right)^2 h^{10} \exp\left(-\frac{h}{1000}\right) + 2.7 \times 10^{-16} \exp\left(-\frac{h}{1500}\right), \quad (17)$$

375 where h [m] is the altitude, v [m/s] is the Root-Mean-Square (RMS) wind-speed, and parameter
 376 $A_0 = C_n^2(h_0)$ [$\text{m}^{-2/3}$] is the nominal value of the refractive index near the ground level. The RMS
 377 wind-speed in (17) is determined from the Bufton wind model, and can take values that range from
 378 $v = 10$ to 30 m/s for moderate and strong wind speeds, respectively. Similarly, the ground turbulence
 379 level can take values between $A_0 = 1.7 \times 10^{-14}$ and $1.7 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$, which depends on the location
 380 and day time, among other parameters.

Figure 5. Refractive index structure $C_n^2(h)$ along the slant path for the H-V day model as function of the altitude. Red lines: $A_0 = 1.7 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$. Green lines: $A_0 = 1.7 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$. Wind speed: $v = 10 \text{ m/s}$ (dotted lines with squares); $v = 21 \text{ m/s}$ (solid-lines with circles); $v = 30 \text{ m/s}$ (dashed lines with diamonds).

When using $A_0 = 1.7 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$ and $v = 21 \text{ m/s}$, this modeled is commonly referred as the H-V_{5/7} model because, for wavelength $\lambda = 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ and a transmitter on the ground looking up (*i.e.*, with $\zeta = 0 \text{ deg.}$), it predicts a value of atmospheric coherence diameter $r_0 = 5 \text{ cm}$ according to (16) and a value of isoplanatic angle

$$\theta_0 = \frac{\cos^{8/5}(\zeta)}{\left[2.91 k^2 \int_{h_0}^H C_n^2(h) (h - h_0)^{5/3} dh\right]^{3/5}} \quad (18)$$

381 of $7 \mu\text{rad}$ in case of a spherical wave with output-plane beam parameters $\Theta = \Lambda = 0$. The refractive
 382 index profile along the vertical/slant path is shown in Fig. 5 for two nominal values of refractive
 383 index at the ground level and three different RMS wind speeds. From this figure, it is possible to observe
 384 that the ground turbulence level A_0 has little effect above 1 km, and that the wind speed governs the
 385 profile behavior primarily in the vicinity of altitudes in the 10 km range.

386 Similarly, Fig. 6 shows the RMS angular displacement due to beam wander (σ_{BW}^2) as function of
 387 the beam radius W_0 , when the operating wavelength $\lambda = 1.55 \mu\text{m}$ and the refractive index structure
 388 $C_n^2(h)$ follows the H-V_{5/7} model. As expected, the RMS beam wander displacement is higher for the
 389 largest zenith angle, as the section of the atmosphere through which the optical beam needs pass
 390 through is thicker, the beam deviation with respect to the straight path grows. Finally, according to (16),
 391 the Fried's coherence length $r_0 = 19.25$ and 12.70 cm for zenith angle $\zeta = 0$ and 60 deg. , respectively.

392
 393 **Turbulence-induced beam spreading:** This phenomenon takes place when the turbulent eddies are
 394 *smaller* than the size of the optical beam. Beam spreading generates a widening of the beam size,
 395 beyond the natural broadening due to diffraction that the non-turbulent atmosphere introduces. Beam
 396 spreading does not affect the direction of the optical beam but, in contrast, reduces the optical power
 397 at the receiver aperture due to the energy dispersion that takes place.

398
 399 **Turbulence-induced beam scintillation:** When the size of turbulent eddies is of the *same order* of the
 400 size of the optical beam, then the eddies act as lenses that focus and defocus the incoming beam. In
 401 this situation, the eddies lead to a redistribution of the signal energy that generates a temporal and
 402 spatial fluctuation of the irradiance at the receiver aperture. This phenomenon, which is known as

Figure 6. RMS angular beam wander (σ_{BW}^2) as function of the beam radius (W_0) for a transmitter in the ground and a satellite in the space assuming $\lambda = 1.55 \mu\text{m}$ and a refractive index structure following the H-V_{5/7} model (wind speed: $v = 21 \text{ m/s}$). Zenith angle: $\zeta = 0 \text{ deg.}$ (solid orange line) and $\zeta = 60 \text{ deg.}$ (dashed purple line).

403 scintillation, represent one of the major sources of degradation in the performance of an optical feeder
 404 link. Atmospheric turbulence also leads to loss of spatial coherence of an initially coherent optical
 405 beam, and may also produce depolarization of the light and temporal stretching of the optical pulse.

The atmospheric scintillation is measured in terms of the scintillation index, which is the normalized variance of the intensity fluctuations, *i.e.*,

$$\sigma_I^2 \triangleq \frac{\langle (I - I_m)^2 \rangle}{I_m^2} = \frac{\langle I^2 \rangle - I_m^2}{I_m^2} = \frac{\langle I^2 \rangle}{I_m^2} - 1, \quad I_m = \langle I \rangle, \quad (19)$$

406 where I is the irradiance (intensity) in the detector plane and $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes the ensemble average.

The Gamma-Gamma distribution has been proposed to describe the turbulence-induced scintillation over a broad range of beam diameters. The Probability Density Function (PDF) of the Gamma-Gamma turbulence model and the scintillation index are given by

$$f_I(x) = \frac{2}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)x} \left(\frac{\alpha\beta x}{I_m} \right)^{\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}} K_{\alpha-\beta} \left(2\sqrt{\frac{\alpha\beta x}{I_m}} \right) \quad x \geq 0, \quad \sigma_I^2 = \frac{1}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{\beta} + \frac{1}{\alpha\beta}, \quad (20)$$

respectively, where I_m denotes the mean irradiance, $\Gamma(x)$ is the Gamma function, $K_n(x)$ is the modified Bessel function of the second kind. The parameters $\alpha = 1/\sigma_X^2$ and $\beta = 1/\sigma_Y^2$ of the Gamma-Gamma distribution in (20) are directly related to the atmospheric conditions, and for the untracked beam case are given

$$\sigma_X^2 = 5.95(H - h_0)^2 \sec^2(\zeta) \left(\frac{2W_0}{r_0} \right)^{5/3} \left(\frac{\alpha_{\text{pe}}}{W} \right)^2 \exp \left\{ \frac{0.49 \sigma_{\text{Bu}}^2}{[1 + (1 + \Theta) 0.56 \sigma_{\text{Bu}}^{12/5}]^{7/6}} \right\} - 1, \quad (21)$$

and

$$\sigma_Y^2 = \exp \left\{ \frac{0.51 \sigma_{\text{Bu}}^2}{[1 + 0.69 \sigma_{\text{Bu}}^{12/5}]^{5/6}} \right\} - 1. \quad (22)$$

The various parameters that appear in equations (21) and (22) are defined as follows:

$$\alpha_{pe} = \sigma_{pe}/L, \quad \sigma_{pe}^2 \cong \sigma_{BW}^2 \left[1 - \left(\frac{C_r^2 W_0^2 / r_0^2}{1 + C_r^2 W_0^2 / r_0^2} \right)^{1/6} \right], \quad L = \frac{H - h_0}{\cos(\zeta)}, \quad C_r = 2\pi, \quad (23)$$

are the jitter-induced angular pointing error, the pointing error variance, slant path length, and scaling constant, respectively. Similarly, the diffractive beam radius at the receiver is given by

$$W = W_0 \sqrt{\Theta_0^2 + \Lambda_0^2}, \quad \text{where} \quad \Theta_0 = 1 - \frac{L}{F_0}, \quad \Lambda_0 = \frac{2L}{kW_0^2} \quad (24)$$

are the *input-plane beam parameters*. Note that for a collimated beam, the phase front radius of curvature at the transmitter output aperture $F_0 \rightarrow \infty$ and, due to that, $\Theta_0 \cong 1$. Finally, the irradiance flux variance in the focal plane of the receiver

$$\sigma_{Bu}^2 = 8.7 k^{7/6} (H - h_0)^{5/6} \sec^{11/6}(\zeta) \times \text{Re} \left\{ \int_{h_0}^H C_n^2(h) \left[\xi^{5/6} [\Lambda \xi + j(1 - \bar{\Theta} \xi)]^{5/6} - \Lambda^{5/6} \xi^{5/3} \right] dh \right\}, \quad (25)$$

where

$$\xi = 1 - \frac{h - h_0}{H - h_0} \quad (26)$$

is the normalized distance for the uplink propagation path, and

$$\bar{\Theta} = 1 - \Theta = 1 - \frac{\Theta_0}{\Theta_0^2 + \Lambda_0^2} = -\frac{L}{F_0}, \quad \Lambda = \frac{\Lambda_0}{\Theta_0^2 + \Lambda_0^2} = \frac{2L}{kW_0^2}, \quad (27)$$

are the *output-plane beam parameters*.

In Fig. 7 we plot the corresponding Gamma-Gamma PDF for three different beam sizes W_0 , which are equal to 1, 10 and 50 cm. Once again, the wavelength was set to $\lambda = 1.55 \mu\text{m}$ and the analysis was done for the uplink direction of communication of a perfectly vertical GEO satellite feeder link (*i.e.*, $\zeta = 0$ deg. and $H = 36000$ km) when using the H-V_{5/7} refractive index model (*i.e.*, $v = 21$ m/s). Note that in this situation, the Fried's coherence length is $r_0 = 19.25$ cm. As expected, for small beam sizes in which the $2W_0/r_0 \ll 1$ relationship is verified (*e.g.*, similar to $W_0 = 1$ cm in Fig. 7), the longitudinal component of the scintillation index will be much less than 1; due to that, the corresponding PDF of the normalized irradiance will have a shape that resembles the one of a log-normal distribution, but with some differences in the upper and lower tails. On the other hand, for large beams in which the $2W_0/r_0 \gg 1$ relationship is observed (*e.g.*, similar to $W_0 = 50$ cm in Fig. 7), the scintillation index becomes larger than 1 and the shape of the PDF starts to resemble a negative exponential distribution.

4. Performance Evaluation

The error correction capabilities that the Modulation and Coding Schemes (MCS) of the NB-IoT (and DVB-S2(X)) standard have on the end-to-end forward link of the GEO satellite system (*i.e.*, from the satellite gateway to the IoT terminals) is now evaluated in detail. For this purpose, we first present the simulation setup and, after that, we show the different figures of merit that are relevant to characterize the end-to-end performance of the three GEO satellite relaying strategies.

4.1. Simulation setup of the Optical channel

According to the analysis presented in [28], the mean SNR of the electrical signal that is direct-detected by the PD that is placed on-board the satellite is given by

$$\text{SNR}_{e,pd} = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{|i_d(t)|^2\}}{\mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\}} \approx \frac{I_D^2 \beta^2}{\mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\}} \quad \beta \ll 1, \quad (28)$$

Figure 7. Gamma-Gamma probability density function for an untracked collimated beam plotted as function of the normalized irradiance for a GEO optical feeder uplink channel with zenith angle $\zeta = 0$ deg. and H-V_{5/7} refractive index structure ($\lambda = 1.55 \mu\text{m}$, $r_0 = 19$ cm). Beam radius: $W_0 = 1$ cm (solid red lines), $W_0 = 10$ cm (dashed green lines), and $W_0 = 50$ cm (dotted blue lines).

where

$$I_D = \mathbb{E}\{i_D(t)\} = \mu \frac{G_{o,\text{tx}} G_{o,\text{rx}} G_{o,\text{edfa}}}{L_{o,\text{fsl}} L_{o,\text{atm}} L_{o,\text{bsl}} L_{o,\text{sys}}} \frac{P_{o,\text{ld}}}{2} \quad (29)$$

is the DC component of the time-varying electrical current $i_D(t)$ that the PD generates when being excited by the intensity modulated optical signal, β is the intensity modulation index, and

$$\mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\} = \mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{shot}}(t)|^2\} + \mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{thermal}}(t)|^2\} + \mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{rin}}(t)|^2\} + \mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{beat}}(t)|^2\} \quad (30)$$

426 includes the contribution of all noise sources in the optical feeder link, namely the *shot noise* sources,
 427 *thermal noise*, *Relative Intensity Noise* (RIN) of LD, and *beat noise* [25]. Note that shot noise term includes
 428 the contribution of the received optical signal, the Amplified Spontaneous Emission (ASE) noise, the
 429 background optical noise and the dark current noise, whereas the beat noise term accounts the effect
 430 of combining the received optical signal with the ASE noise.

When the received optical power is between -90 and -20 dBW, it can be shown that the beat noise between received optical signal and ASE noise dominates the SNR performance of the optical feeder link [47]. In this situation,

$$\mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\} \approx \mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{beat}}(t)|^2\} = i_{\text{sig-sp}}^2 + i_{\text{sp-sp}}^2 \approx i_{\text{sig-sp}}^2 = 4 I_D I_{\text{ase}} (B_e / B_o), \quad (31)$$

431 where B_o is the bandwidth of the optical signal at the PD input, B_e is the bandwidth of the electrical
 432 signal at the PD output, and $I_{\text{ase}} = \mu G_{o,\text{edfa}} P_{\text{ase}}$ is the DC component generated by the ASE noise,
 433 whose equivalent noise power at the input of the EDFA is given by $P_{\text{ase}} = \rho_{\text{ase}} B_o$.

Table 2 summarizes the parameters of the optical feeder link, taking into account both the optical gains and losses, as well as the different sources of optical noise [25,48]. Note that the values of the parameters that appear in this table have been determined taking into account the different phenomena described in Section 3, when modeling the contribution of each of them in the space-to-ground optical link budget. The effect of any other parameter not listed in this table is considered as negligible. When $L_{o,\text{atm}} = 0$ dB (*i.e.*, clear-sky conditions), the DC current at the PD output is $I_D = 75.68$ mA, whereas the

Table 2. Parameters of the optical feeder link used in the NB-IoT satellite system and associated power budget.

Symbol	Optical Link Parameter	Value	Unit
$P_{o,ld}$	Optical power of LD (including EDFA booster)	47.0	dBm
$G_{o,tx}$	Optical gain of transmitter (ground telescope)	110.9	dB
$G_{o,rx}$	Optical gain of receiver (satellite telescope)	112.8	dB
$L_{o,fsl}$	Free space loss of optical link ($\lambda = 1550$ nm, $H = 36000$ km)	289.8	dB
$L_{o,atm}$	Atmospheric attenuation (absorption and scattering)	0-10	dB
$L_{o,bsl}$	Beam spreading loss due to scintillation	1.6	dB
$L_{o,sys}$	System losses in the optical feeder link	4.5	dB
G_{edfa}	Gain of the optical amplifier (EDFA)	50.0	dB
μ	Responsivity of photodetector (PIN diode)	0.5	A/W
B_e	Bandwidth of electrical filter (PD output)	1.5	GHz
B_o	Bandwidth of optical channel ($\lambda = 1550$ nm)	12.5	GHz
ρ_{ase}	PSD of amplified spontaneous emissions	2.0×10^{-19}	W/Hz
ρ_{rin}	PSD of RIN process (normalized)	-160	dBc/Hz
ρ_{back}	PSD of background noise at EDFA input	7.6×10^{-25}	W/Hz
i_n	Electrical noise current spectral density	1.0×10^{-11}	A
i_{dark}	Dark current at the PIN diode output	1.0×10^{-10}	A

DC current generated by the ASE noise is $I_{ase} = 0.125$ mA regardless of the weather. Thus, when we set the intensity modulation index $\beta = 0.5$, the SNR of the electrical signal at the PD output becomes

$$\text{SNR}_{e,pd}[\text{dB}] = 25.01[\text{dB}] - L_{o,atm}[\text{dB}]. \quad (32)$$

434 Note that for larger intensity modulation indexes β , the non-linear distortion introduced by the
 435 Match-Zehnder Modulator (MZM) of the optical transmitter becomes more notable. For those situation,
 436 the use of Digital Pre-Distortion (DPD) is necessary to keep non-linear distortion under control [25].

437 Fig. 8 shows the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of the power loss that
 438 turbulence-induced beam wander and beam scintillation introduce on the received optical power of the
 439 optical uplink transmission in the satellite forward link (see Section 3). Without loss of generalization,
 440 it is assumed that the ground station is placed next to the city of Madrid, Spain (*i.e.*, Lat. 40.43° North,
 441 Long. 4.25° West, and altitude $h_0 = 864$ m), with an expected system availability due to cloud-free
 442 line-of-sight conditions close to 99.8%. Similarly, the satellite is assumed to be placed in the GEO
 443 position of 19.2° East at an altitude of $H = 36000$ km, giving as result a zenith angle $\zeta = 52.61$ deg. for
 444 the optical feeder link in the forward direction of communication. The nominal value of the refractive
 445 index near the ground level is always $A_0 = 1.7 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$, and the CDF is plotted for three
 446 different wind speeds (*i.e.*, $v = 10, 21$ and 30 m/s). Note that when $v = 21$ m/s, the refractive index
 447 model becomes the well-known H- $V_{5/7}$ model. Finally, an untracked collimated beam is assumed,
 448 with a beam radius of $W_0 = 10$ cm at a wavelength of $\lambda = 1550$ nm. As expected, the stronger is the
 449 wind speed, the more variability is introduced in the instantaneous intensity of the received optical
 450 signal at the GEO satellite. For example, the 10-th percentile for the turbulence-induced power loss
 451 (*i.e.*, power loss margin for a 90% link availability without coding) is equal to 2.4, 3.0 and 3.8 dB for a
 452 wind speed of 10, 21 and 30 m/s, respectively. These turbulence-induced power losses grow to 4.3,
 453 5.4 and 7.0 dB when we study the 1-st percentile (*i.e.*, power loss margin for a 99% link availability
 454 without coding) for the same three values of wind speeds (*i.e.*, 10, 21 and 30 m/s, respectively).

455 4.2. Simulation setup of NB-IoT signal

456 This paper evaluates the BLER and Throughput of the following three forward link architectures
 457 for transmitting NB-IoT over satellite when the feeder link is optical:

- 458 1. Case 1: NB-IoT detect-and-forward (See Section 2.2.1).
- 459 2. Case 2: NB-IoT decode-and-forward (See Section 2.2.2).

Figure 8. Cumulative distribution function of the power loss that turbulence-induced beam wander and scintillation introduces in the uplink direction of the optical feeder link in case of an untracked collimated beam with $\lambda = 1.55 \mu\text{m}$, $W_0 = 10 \text{ cm}$, $\zeta = 52.61 \text{ deg}$, $A_0 = 1.7 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$. The ground station site is assumed next to Madrid ($h_0 = 864 \text{ m}$) and the position of the GEO satellite is assumed at 19.2° East ($H = 36000 \text{ km}$). Wind speeds: $v = 10 \text{ m/s}$ (solid red line), $v = 21 \text{ m/s}$ (dashed green line), and $v = 30 \text{ m/s}$ (dashed-dotted line).

460 3. Case 3: NB-IoT encapsulated in DVB-S2(X) frames. DVB-S2(X) decode and NB-IoT detect-and- forward
461 (See Section 2.2.3).

462 In all cases the frame length of the NB-IoT has been kept constant to $N=1032$ bits. The pulse-shape
463 for NB-IoT and DVB-S2(X) waveforms is the square-root rise cosine filter (RRC) with a roll-off factor
464 of $\rho=0.15$. The tested time-packed overlapping factor, denoted as δ , takes the following values
465 $\delta = \{0, 15, 25, 40\} \%$. Note that the time-packed symbol time for the case of $\delta=0\%$ collapses to the
466 Nyquist symbol-time. The modulation of the optical feeder links is 4-PAM since it is used Intensity
467 Modulation/Direct Detection scheme. On the contrary, the access link uses QPSK modulation which
468 corresponds to the NB-IoT's one for the down-link. Therefore, in both links the number of modulation
469 states is $M=4$ and the number of bits per modulated symbol is $N_b=2$.

In order to compare in a fair way all architectures they use the same data rate. Furthermore, it has not been considered an unique data rate but multiple ones. In particular, it has been tested the BLER and throughput of the aforementioned cases for nine possible code rates. Three code rates lower than the mother code rate of the convolutional encoding (*i.e.*, 0.2222, 0.259, and 0.3), three medium code rates (*i.e.*, 0.4444, 0.5319, and 0.6) and three high code rates (*i.e.*, 0.6386, 0.7678 and 0.854). For the first and second use cases these code rates correspond to the code rate of the NB-IoT waveform. However, for the third case, these code rates represent the joint code rate of the DVB-S2(X) and NB-IoT waveforms. This joint code rate is defined as the product between the code rates of the DVB-S2(X) and NB-IoT signals as

$$R_{c_{\text{Case 3}}} = R_{c_{\text{NB-IoT}}} \times R_{c_{\text{DVB-S2(X)}}} \quad (33)$$

470 In (33) it has been selected the code rates of NB-IoT and DVB-S2(X) such that the their joint code
471 rate, *i.e.* $R_{c_{\text{Case 3}}}$, is equal to the code rates of NB-IoT for the first and second cases. Thus, it has
472 been considered three code rates (*i.e.* low, medium and high) for each waveform (*i.e.* NB-IoT and
473 DVB-S2(X)) which permit to obtain the nine code rates for cases 1 and 2. Specifically, the used code
474 rates of the DVB-S2(X) and NB-IoT are: $R_{c_{\text{DVB-S2(X)}}} = \{0.66667, 0.8, \text{ and } 0.9\}$ [33] and $R_{c_{\text{NB-IoT}}} = \{0.3333,$
475 $0.66667, \text{ and } 0.96\}$ respectively. Thus we obtain nine possible combinations of the code rates being the
476 equivalent code rates among all transmission architectures (see Table 3 for more details).

Table 3. NB-IoT and DVB-S2(X) equivalent code rates for the relaying architectures under analysis.

$R_{c, dvb}$	$R_{c, iot}$	$R_{c, case3}$	$R_{c, case1/2}$
0.66667	0.33333	0.2222	0.2222
0.8	0.33333	0.2667	0.259
0.9	0.33333	0.3	0.3
0.66667	0.66667	0.4444	0.4444
0.8	0.66667	0.5333	0.5319
0.9	0.66667	0.6	0.6
0.66667	0.96	0.64	0.6386
0.8	0.96	0.768	0.7678
0.9	0.96	0.864	0.8628

Table 4. Maximum achievable throughput in terms of the overlapping factor and code rate.

R_c	$\delta = 0\%$	$\delta = 15\%$	$\delta = 25\%$	$\delta = 40\%$
0.2222	0.3864	0.4546	0.5152	0.6441
0.2590	0.4504	0.5299	0.6006	0.7507
0.3000	0.5217	0.6138	0.6957	0.8696
0.4444	0.7729	0.9093	1.0305	1.2881
0.5319	0.9250	1.0883	1.2334	1.5417
0.6000	1.0435	1.2276	1.3913	1.7391
0.6386	1.1106	1.3066	1.4808	1.8510
0.7678	1.3353	1.5709	1.7804	2.2255
0.8628	1.5005	1.7653	2.0007	2.5009

So, after obtaining a similar code rate for the three cases under study, it will be determined the architecture that provides the best performance in terms of BLER and Throughput in terms of the up-link and down-link SNRs. Regarding the Throughput, it has been used the following expression for measuring it:

$$THR(\delta, R_c) = \frac{N_b \cdot R_c \cdot (1 - BLER)}{(1 + \rho) \cdot (1 - \delta)}, \quad (34)$$

477 where in (34) the code rate R_c for the two first cases under study corresponds to the code rate of the
 478 NB-IoT waveform. For the third case, the value of R_c represents the joint code rate of the NB-IoT and
 479 DVB-S2(X) waveforms, which has been formulated in (33). The roll-off will be left constant for all
 480 simulations and equal to $\rho = 0.15$. Thus, according to the possible overlapping factors and code rates,
 481 the maximum achievable throughput can be obtained (see Table 4 for further details).

482 This maximum achievable throughput may not been achieved due to the presence of a residual
 483 time-packing interference, optical channel variation, and the noise in the up-link and feeder link
 484 may increase the BLER. So, simulation results will provide information about the transmission
 485 structure that provides the best performance in terms of BLER and Throughput. Note that low code
 486 rates provide very low BLER but the worse results in terms of throughput. On the contrary, high
 487 code rates may provide the highest achievable throughput but the worse BLER. For that reason
 488 it has been considered the BLER of 10^{-2} as the target BLER according to 5G specifications for
 489 providing normal services. This helps to decide the best transmission architecture. The case that
 490 satisfies the target BLER and provides the best throughput will be the best transmission architecture.
 491 Consequently, it is a mix between BLER and throughput. However, in order to compare the three
 492 cases under study is necessary to define additional figures of merit. The following section defines them.

493 494 4.3. Definition of the Figures of merit.

From previous section we have defined the throughput in terms of the overlapping factor and code rate. However, in the evaluation process of the three cases will be interested in the envelope of the throughput defined in (34). Specifically, we will be interested in the envelope of the throughput

when it is left constant the overlapping factor. This throughput, denoted as $THR(\delta)^*$, is defined as the maximum throughput for all code rates with the same overlapping factor and it is computed as:

$$THR(\delta)^* = \max_{\mathbf{R}_c} \{THR(\delta, \mathbf{R}_c)\}. \quad (35)$$

Next we will be interested in determining the throughput's envelope for the no-time and time packing schemes. For the case of no-time packing, the envelope of its throughput, denoted as THR_{NTP} , is obtained by particularizing (35) for $\delta=0$, i.e. $THR_{NTP} = THR(\delta = 0)^*$. For the case of time-packing, its throughput's envelope, denoted as THR_{TP} , will be determined by computing the maximum of (35) for all overlapping factors higher than zero, $\delta>0$, as follows:

$$THR_{TP} = \max_{\delta>0} \{THR(\delta)^*\}. \quad (36)$$

Then, the total throughput's envelope for a particular case will be obtained from the maximum envelope's throughput of the time-packed and non-time packed ones as:

$$THR_{Case\ q} = \max\{THR_{NTP}, THR_{TP}\}. \quad (37)$$

After defining alternative the envelope's of the throughput, we introduce two measures relatives to the gains in throughput. The first one measures if using time-packing is beneficial respect to non-time-packing. It provides a percentage of gain in throughput, denoted as $G_{THR}(\%)$, and it is computed as:

$$G_{THR}(\%) = \frac{(THR_{TP} - THR_{NTP}) \times 100}{THR_{NTP}}. \quad (38)$$

The second gain in throughput is related about measuring the best system. From the three cases, the first one it is the simplest one since the satellite does not manipulate it. So, it has been considered as the benchmark system. Then, it will be computed the relative gain of cases 2 and 3 respect to case 1. This gain is denoted as $\Delta G_{THRq,1}(\%)$, which represents the gain in envelope of case q , with $q \in \{2, 3\}$ respect to case 1. Also it is given in percentage and it is formulated as:

$$\Delta G_{THRq,1}(\%) = \frac{(THR_{Case\ q} - THR_{Case\ 1}) \times 100}{THR_{Case\ 1}}, \quad (39)$$

495 being $THR_{Case\ q}$ and $THR_{Case\ 1}$ the throughput's envelope for all cases under study computed following
 496 (37). Finally, after defining the figures of merit for analyzing the simulation results, we present the
 497 obtained results in the next section.

498 4.4. Simulation Results

499 The results provided in this section evaluate the BLER and Throughput of the three
 500 aforementioned architectures in the following aspects:

- 501 1. Evaluation the end-end BLER and Throughput when the E_b/N_0 of the feeder links varies from 2
 502 to 22 dB in steps of 1 dB (see Fig. 9), the SNR of the access link is 20 dB, the wind speed of the
 503 clouds is 21 m/s, and the NB-IoT code rates are: $\mathbf{R}_{c_{NB-IoT}} = \{0.3333, 0.66667 \text{ and } 0.95556\}$. There is
 504 no time-packing (i.e., $\delta = 0\%$) and the tested configuration is case 1 (i.e., Detect-and-Forward
 505 NB-IoT). The throughput of Fig. 9 is the $THR(\delta = 0, \mathbf{R}_{c_{NB-IoT}})$ of (34).
- 506
 507 2. Evaluation the end-end Throughput and BLER when the E_b/N_0 of the access links varies from
 508 -8 to 12 dB in steps of 1 dB (see Fig. 10), the SNR of the feeder link is 15, 20 and 25 dB, the wind
 509 speed is $v = 10, 21$ and 30 m/s, and the NB-IoT code rates are: $\mathbf{R}_{c_{NB-IoT}} = \{0.3333, 0.66667 \text{ and } 0.95556\}$. There is
 510 no time-packing (i.e., $\delta = 0\%$) and the tested configuration is the use case 1, i.e.
 511 Detect-and-Forward NB-IoT. The throughput of Fig. 10 is the $THR(\delta = 0, \mathbf{R}_{c_{NB-IoT}})$ of (34).

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3. Evaluation of the Throughput (see Fig. 11) and BLER (see Fig. 17) and for the Case 1: Detect-and-Forward NB-IoT when the SNR of the feeder link is 15 dB, the E_b/N_0 of the access varies from -8 to 12 dB, and the code rates of the NB-IoT and overlapping factors defined in Section 4.2. The throughput of Fig. 11 corresponds to $THR(\delta, \mathbf{R}_{c_{NB-IoT}})$ of (34).
4. Evaluation of the Throughput (see Fig. 12) and BLER (see Fig. 18) and for the Case 2: Decode-and-Forward NB-IoT when the SNR of the feeder link is 15 dB, the SNR of the access varies from 0 to 20 dB, and the code rates of the NB-IoT and overlapping factors defined in Section 4.2. The throughput of Fig. 12 corresponds to $THR(\delta, \mathbf{R}_{c_{NB-IoT}})$ of (34).
5. Evaluation of the Throughput (See Fig. 14) and BLER (See Fig. 19) and for the Case 3: Detect-and-Forward NB-IoT encapsulated in DVB-S2(X) frames when the SNR of the feeder link is 15 dB, the SNR of the access varies from 0 to 20 dB, and the code rates of the DVB-S2(X) and NB-IoT and overlapping factors defined in section 4.2. The throughput of Fig. 14 corresponds to $THR(\delta, \mathbf{R}_{c_{NB-IoT}})$ of (34).
6. Evaluation of the Throughput's envelope when it is left constant the overlapping factor for all cases under study (See Fig. 13a,13b,13c) when the SNR of feeder link is 15 dB, the SNR of the access varies from 0 to 20 dB, and the code rates of the DVB-S2(X) and NB-IoT and overlapping factors defined in section 4.2. The throughput of these figures corresponds to $THR(\delta)^*$ of (35).
7. Evaluation of the gain in throughput using time-packing respect to no-time packing is shown in Fig. 13d. The SNR of feeder link is 15 dB, the SNR of the access varies from 0 to 20 dB. This gain is denoted as $G_{THR}(\%)$ and computed following (38).
8. Comparison among Envelope of the Throughput for all cases under study (See Fig. 15a,15b,15c,15d) in terms of the overlapping factor, when the SNR of feeder link is 15 dB, the SNR of the access varies from 0 to 20 dB, and the code rates of the DVB-S2(X) and NB-IoT and overlapping factors defined in section 4.2. The throughput of these figures corresponds to $THR(\delta)^*$ of (35).
9. Comparison of the envelope of the Throughput for all cases under study (See Fig. 16a) when the SNR of feeder link is 15 dB, the SNR of the access varies from 0 to 20 dB. The throughput plotted in this figure is denoted as $THR_{Case\ q}$ and computed according to (37).
10. Comparison of the gain in throughput that offer cases 2 and 3 respect to case 1 (See Fig. 16b) when the SNR of feeder link is 15 dB, the SNR of the access varies from 0 to 20 dB. This gain in throughput of this figure is denoted as $\Delta G_{THRq,1}$ with $q \in \{2,3\}$, and determined following (39).

Figure 9. End-to-end BLER (left) and throughput (right) versus E_b/N_0 in the access link for a NB-IoT frame ($SNR_{\text{access}} = 20$ dB). NB-IoT code rates: 0.33333 (square), 0.66667 (circle), 0.95556 (diamond), when the wind speed is $v = 21$ m/s. Solid lines with filled markers: BLER 10^{-2} requirement fulfilled. Dashed-lines with unfilled markers: BLER 10^{-2} requirement not fulfilled. Diameter of aperture's telescope: $W_0 = 21$ cm.

551 From the simulations of the end-end BLER and Throughput in terms of the SNR of the up-link
 552 for a very high SNR of the access link, (See Fig. 9), then it is possible to observe region in which the
 553 up-link limits the transmission. In all plots the dotted lines means that the BLER is higher than the
 554 target BLER whereas the continuous ones represent that their BLER is lower than the target BLER, i.e.
 555 0.01. For a better indication, the grey area in the figure of BLER show the region of SNRs for which the
 556 tested code rates for NB-IoT satisfies the target BLER. Thus, it is possible to observe that the code
 557 rate of $R_{c_{\text{NB-IoT}}}=0.3333$ provides the best throughput when the SNR of the feeder link is ranged
 558 between 13 and 19 dB, $R_{c_{\text{NB-IoT}}}=0.6666$ is the best option when the feeder's link SNR is between 19
 559 and 22 dB, and finally $R_{c_{\text{NB-IoT}}}=0.95556$ is the best one when the up-link SNR is larger than 22 dB.
 560 According to this result we have chosen the SNR of the feeder link of 15, 20 and 25 dB for determining
 561 the degradation of the end-end link in terms of the wind speed.

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563 Fig. 10 evaluates the degradation of the BLER (Figures at the left) and throughput (Figures at the
 564 right) when the wind speed is 10, 21, 30 m/s for the up-link SNRs of 15, 20, and 25 dB. Simulation
 565 results show that the higher is the SNR of the feeder link, the lower is the degradation of the end-end
 566 BLER and Throughput due to the wind speed of the clouds. Consequently, it has been motivated to
 567 use the SNR of 15 dB as the reference SNR for using in the feeder link in the comparison of the three
 568 satellite architectures.

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(f) Throughput for $\delta = 0\%$. $SNR_{up}=25$ dB

Figure 10. End-to-end BLER (left) and throughput (right) versus E_b/N_0 in the access link for a NB-IoT frame ($SNR_{feeder} = 15, 20$ and 25 dB). NB-IoT code rates: 0.33333 (square), 0.66667 (circle), 0.95556 (diamond), when the wind speed is $v = 10$ m/s (red), $v = 21$ m/s (blue) and $v = 30$ m/s (magenta). Solid lines with filled markers: BLER 10^{-2} requirement fulfilled. Dashed-lines with unfilled markers: BLER 10^{-2} requirement not fulfilled. Diameter of aperture's telescope: $W_0 = 10$ cm.

Figure 11. End-to-end throughput versus E_b/N_0 in the access link for a NB-IoT frame ($SNR_{\text{feeder}} = 15$ dB). NB-IoT code rates: 0.2222 (red square), 0.259 (red circle), 0.3 (red diamond), 0.444 (blue square), 0.5319 (blue circle), 0.6 (blue diamond), 0.6386 (magenta square), 0.7678 (magenta circle), 0.8628 (magenta diamond). Solid lines with filled markers: BLER 10^{-2} requirement fulfilled. Dashed-lines with unfilled markers: BLER 10^{-2} requirement not fulfilled. Wind speed: $v = 21$ m/s and diameter of aperture's telescope: $W_0 = 10$ cm.

570 Fig. 11 shows the throughput for each overlapping factor and code rate, whereas Fig. 13a plots
 571 the envelope's throughput for all overlapping factor for the case 1: Detect-and-forward with NB-IoT.
 572 Simulation results show that the unique segment of NB-IoT code rates that satisfies the target BLER is
 573 the lowest one, *i.e.*, $R_{c_{\text{NB-IoT}}} = \{0.2222, 0.259, \text{ and } 0.3\}$ for all time-packing overlapping. The medium
 574 code rate of $R_c = 0.4444$ is able to achieve its maximum throughput only when there is no overlapping
 575 (*i.e.* $\delta = 0\%$). Medium and larger code rates are mainly penalized by the SNR of the up-link and are not
 576 able to achieve their maximum throughput (see Table 4). Comparing the performance of time-packing
 577 schemes vs no-time-packing ones, results show that in all cases time-packing schemes show a better
 578 throughput. However, it depends on the E_b/N_0 of the access. Towards this regard, Fig. 13d shows
 579 the % of gain in throughput of the time-packed vs no time-packed signalling. There it is possible
 580 to observe that for the set of E_b/N_0 ranged between -2 and 5 dB the gain in envelope's throughput
 581 of time-packed schemes versus no-time-packed ones is around 50% of average. For other values of
 582 E_b/N_0 the % of gain in throughput falls down to only a 10%.

Figure 12. End-to-end throughput versus E_b/N_0 in the access link for a NB-IoT frame in a regenerative satellite (decode forward) ($\text{SNR}_{\text{feeder}} = 15$ dB). NB-IoT code rates: 0.2222 (red square), 0.259 (red circle), 0.3 (red diamond), 0.444 (blue square), 0.5319 (blue circle), 0.6 (blue diamond), 0.6386 (magenta square), 0.7678 (magenta circle), 0.8628 (magenta diamond). Solid lines with filled markers: BLER 10^{-2} requirement fulfilled. Dashed-lines with unfilled markers: BLER 10^{-2} requirement not fulfilled. Wind speed: $v = 21$ m/s and diameter of aperture's telescope: $W_0 = 10$ cm.

583 Fig. 12, Fig. 13b and Fig. 13d show the throughput for each code rate and overlapping factor,
 584 envelope's throughput and the % in gain of throughput of time-packed schemes vs no time packed
 585 ones for case 2: decode-and-forward NB-IoT. From Fig. 12 it is possible to observe that the regeneration
 586 of the NB-IoT signal at the satellite permits to use also medium code rates with time-packing of
 587 $\delta=\{0,15\}\%$, i.e. $R_{c_{\text{NB-IoT}}}=0.4444$. So, it means that the largest throughput is not obtained with the largest
 588 overlapping factor (i.e. $\delta=40\%$) and low code rates (i.e. $R_{c_{\text{NB-IoT}}}=0.3$) as in the previous case, but with
 589 moderate overlapping factors (i.e. $\delta=15\%$) and medium code rates (i.e. $R_{c_{\text{NB-IoT}}}=0.4444$). Comparing
 590 the % of the envelope's throughput of the time-packed schemes vs no time-packed ones, observe
 591 that also this gain strongly depends of the E_b/N_0 of the access link. Specifically, from Fig. 13d we
 592 can conclude that for E_b/N_0 ranged between -4 and 1 dB, the % gain in throughput of time-packed
 593 schemes is larger that 40%. For E_b/N_0 larger than 1 dB, the % gain in throughput is around 20%.

(a) Envelope of Throughput Case 1

(b) Envelope of Throughput Case 2

(c) Envelope of Throughput Case 3

(d) Gain in Throughput all cases

Figure 13. End-to-end envelope of throughput (left-hand side), and end-to-end gain in the envelope of throughput of time-packed vs. no-time-packed (right-hand side), represented as function of the E_b/N_0 in the access link for case 3. Overlapping of $\delta = 0\%$ (solid red line), $\delta = 15\%$ (dotted blue line), $\delta = 25\%$ (dashed cyan line), and $\delta = 40\%$ (dashed-dotted magenta line). Sub-figure 13d shows the gain in throughput of time-packed with respect to no-time-packed; here, case 1) is represented in continuous purple line, case 2) is plotted in dotted brown line, and case 3) is shown in dashed green line. Wind speed: $v = 21$ m/s; Beam width: $W_0 = 10$ cm.

595 Fig. 14, Fig. 13c and Fig. 13d plot the throughput in terms of the code rate for each overlapping
 596 factor, envelope's throughput and % of gain in throughput for the time-packed vs no-time packed
 597 schemes respectively for the case 3: decoded DVB-S2(X) and detect-and-forward NB-IoT. Fig. 14 shows
 598 that the best code rate to use in the optical feeder link is $R_{CDVB-S2X}=0.6666$. For the NB-IoT system the
 599 best option is $R_{CNB-IoT}=0.3333$, for an E_b/N_0 ranged between -1 and 5 dB, a $R_{CNB-IoT}=0.6666$, for an
 600 E_b/N_0 between -5 and 9 dB, and $R_{CNB-IoT}=0.96$ for E_b/N_0 larger than 9 dB. Regarding the envelope's
 601 throughput, Fig. 13c indicates that similarly to case 1, it is better to use the largest overlapping
 602 factor (i.e. $\delta=40\%$) to obtain the highest throughput. Comparing the throughput from time-packed
 603 and no-time packed, observe in Fig. 13d that for an E_b/N_0 larger than 0 dB the minimum gain in
 604 throughput is 40%. So, this case provides the largest gain in throughput. However, the minimum
 605 E_b/N_0 to use time-packing is larger than in the other two previous cases.

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Figure 14. End-to-end throughput versus E_b/N_0 in the access link for a NB-IoT frame encapsulated in a DVB-S2(X) satellite frame ($SNR_{\text{feeder}} = 15$ dB). NB-IoT code rates: 1/3 (red), 2/3 (blue), 0.96 (magenta). DVB-S2(X) code rates: 2/3 (squares), 0.8 (circles), 0.9 (diamonds). Solid lines with filled markers: BLER 10^{-2} requirement fulfilled. Dashed-lines with unfilled markers: BLER 10^{-2} requirement not fulfilled. Wind speed: $v = 21$ m/s and diameter of aperture's telescope: $W_0 = 10$ cm.

607 Fig. 15 shows the envelope of the throughput for all cases in terms of the overlapping factor. From
 608 these figures it is possible to observe that for cases 1 and 3 the larger the overlapping factor, the larger
 609 the maximum throughput (i.e. $\delta = 40\%$). On the contrary for case 2, the maximum throughput is
 610 achieved when the overlapping factor is $\delta = 15\%$. Next, Fig. 16 plots the envelope of the throughput
 611 for all cases (Fig. 16a) and the % gain of cases 2 and 3 respect to case 1 (Fig. 16b). From Fig. 16a is
 612 possible to conclude that cases 2 and 3 always have a better throughput than case 1. So, case 1 will
 613 be the benchmark case for determining the goodness of cases 2 and 3. Note also from this figure that
 614 the regeneration of the NB-IoT signal permits to lower the minimum E_b/N_0 around 1.5 dB and 4 dB
 615 respect to case 1 and 3 respectively. Regarding the gain in throughput of cases 2 and 3 respect to case
 616 1, for E_b/N_0 lower than -2 dB the best option is to use case 2, for an E_b/N_0 ranged between -2 and 4
 617 dB case 2 and 3 provide practically the same throughput. Finally, for E_b/N_0 larger than 4 dB the best
 618 strategy is to encapsulate the NB-IoT frames into the DVB-S2(X) ones (case 3).

(d) $\delta = 40\%$ (high overlapping)

Figure 15. End-to-end envelope of throughput for all cases under study versus E_b/N_0 in the access link. Case 1 (continuous red line), Case 2 (dotted blue line) and Case 3 (dashed magenta line). Wind speed: $v = 21$ m/s and diameter of aperture's telescope: $W_0 = 10$ cm.

619 5. Conclusion and Futures Extensions

620 This section presents the main conclusions of the paper and possible future research lines to
 621 extend this work.

622 5.1. Concluding remarks

623 The bottleneck that future mobile systems will have to implement OTA applications in a global
 624 scale, such as software and firmware updates for autonomous driving, is foreseen to be in the feeder
 625 link of the satellite communication systems. To tackle this issue, the use of optical wireless technologies
 626 has been seriously considered to implement the feeder link and satisfy the high data rate demand
 627 that will be required. Towards this regard, this paper presents the closed-form formulas that estimate
 628 the impairments that are introduced in the optical uplink transmission in terms of the wind speed,
 629 wavelength of the optical signal, beam width and telescope aperture, refractive index structure of the

Figure 16. End-to-end envelope of throughput for all cases under study versus E_b/N_0 in the access link. Case 1 (continuous red line), Case 2 (dotted blue line) and Case 3 (dashed magenta line) (Left size). At the right size, gain in the end-to-ends throughput of cases 2 (continuous red line) and 3 (dashed blue line) respect case 1. Wind speed: $v = 21$ m/s and diameter of aperture's telescope: $W_0 = 10$ cm.

630 atmosphere, and azimuth angle of transmission, among others. Furthermore, the use of time-packing
 631 has been also considered to increase the spectral efficiency of the optical feeder link even further. Three
 632 different relaying strategies have been analyzed for the GEO satellite, namely: 1) *Detect-and-Forward*
 633 with NB-IoT; 2) *Decode-and-Forward* with NB-IoT; 3) *Decode-and-Forward* with NB-IoT/DVB-S2(X). From
 634 the simulation results that were obtained, it was possible to conclude that the wind speed has little
 635 effect on the end-to-end performance for mean SNR values larger than 20 dB in the optical feeder link.
 636 For this reason, the performance of the different relaying strategies has been studied in further details
 637 for the optical feeder link at 15 dB (*i.e.*, up to 10 dB atmospheric loss in the optical link budget).

638 For fair comparisons among all the cases under study, similar code rate have been included.
 639 For *Detect-and-Forward* and *Decode-and-Forward* relaying architectures with NB-IoT, these code rates
 640 correspond to the ones defined in the NB-IoT standard. In contrast, for *Decode-and-Forward* with
 641 NB-IoT/DVB-S2(X), the equivalent code rate is equal to the product between the code rates of the
 642 DVB-S2(X) and NB-IoT frames, which can be obtained by using two MCS with high code rates. After
 643 evaluating these relaying configurations, it was possible to conclude that the *Detect-and-Forward*
 644 with NB-IoT achieved its larger throughput when using the lowest NB-IoT code rate and the largest
 645 overlapping factor. In contrast, the relaying architecture based on *Decode-and-Forward* with NB-IoT
 646 obtained its largest throughput when using intermediate code rates and intermediate overlapping
 647 factors. Finally, for the *Decode-and-Forward* with NB-IoT/DVB-S2(X) relaying architecture, the largest
 648 throughput was obtained when using an intermediate code rate for DVB-S2(X), with a variable code
 649 rate for NB-IoT that was adjusted according to the E_b/N_0 in the radio access links. In this latter case,
 650 the larger the E_b/N_0 , the higher the code rate that NB-IoT should use. Regarding the most convenient
 651 overlapping factor, the highest throughput was observed when using the largest overlapping factors.

652 All the proposed relaying architectures were evaluated assuming time-packed signalling in the
 653 optical feeder link. The ISI introduced by time-packing was mitigated using an adaptive MMSE
 654 equalizer. From simulations, it was concluded that the use of time-packing increases the throughput in
 655 all proposed regenerative strategies under study, when compared to the cases in which time-packing
 656 was not used. However, this performance gain was depended on the E_b/N_0 of the access link. For
 657 *Detect-and-Forward* with NB-IoT, this gain varied from 10% to 50-65% for low and medium E_b/N_0 in
 658 the access link, respectively. For *Decode-and-Forward* with NB-IoT, the gain in throughput observed

659 with time-packed signalling with respect to no-time packed went from 45-65% for low E_b/N_0 of the
 660 access link to 10% for medium-to-large E_b/N_0 values. Therefore, the decoding of the information
 661 permits to achieve higher gains at lower E_b/N_0 . However, at larger E_b/N_0 , the performance behavior
 662 of time-packed and no-time-packed signals is quite high and, as consequence, the improvement
 663 in throughput when comparing both schemes is reduced. Finally, for the *Decode-and-Forward* with
 664 NB-IoT/DVB-S2(X), the gain in throughput varies between 50-65% for medium E_b/N_0 values in the
 665 access link to 45% for high E_b/N_0 ones. In this scenario, the large error correction capability of LDPC
 666 codes enables to remove the residual ISI that the equalizer is not able to eliminate. Consequently, it can
 667 deal successfully with the strong ISI that time-packing with large overlapping factors introduce.

668 Next, when comparing the aggregate throughput that the three relaying strategies offer, it can
 669 be concluded that the ones based on the *Decode-and-Forward* architecture provide the largest values.
 670 Specifically, the *Decode-and-Forward* with NB-IoT offers a better throughput for low E_b/N_0 in the
 671 access link, whereas the *Decode-and-Forward* with NB-IoT/DVB-S2(X) provides a larger throughput for
 672 medium-to-high E_b/N_0 values. Note that *Decode-and-Forward* with NB-IoT regenerates the NB-IoT
 673 signal in the satellite, whereas the *Decode-and-Forward* with NB-IoT/DVB-S2(X) protects the NB-IoT
 674 symbols by introducing the code rate of DVB-S2(X) in the optical feeder link. In this situation, when the
 675 E_b/N_0 of the access link was low, the LDPC decoder of DVB-S2(X) did not converge and, due to that, it
 676 introduced errors in the NB-IoT frames that were decoded on-board the satellite for re-transmission in
 677 the radio access link. In this situation, these NB-IoT frames were protected with a code rate larger than
 678 their equivalent for the other cases; therefore, it can be concluded that at low E_b/N_0 in the radio access
 679 link, the *Case 3* relaying strategy is not the optimum one. However, when the E_b/N_0 of the access
 680 increased, the LDPC decoder started to converge and, due to that, it managed to remove the erroneous
 681 bits that were introduced by the optical feeder link in the NB-IoT frames that were encapsulated in the
 682 DVB-S2(X) signal. Here, as the NB-IoT frames had a higher code rate than the code rates that were
 683 used for other configurations, it offered the largest throughput performance.

684 Finally, it is remarked that the link layer should be prepared for adjusting dynamically the
 685 transmission architecture according to the E_b/N_0 of the access link. Therefore, it would be necessary a
 686 control channel from the NB-IoT terminals to the gateway, such that the estimated E_b/N_0 of the access
 687 link can be known in advance when selecting the MCS of the NB-IoT frame, enabling to improve
 688 the end-end throughput. In all cases, the IoT terminal would receive the data in NB-IoT signalling
 689 format. Note that all required modifications of *Decode-and-Forward* of NB-IoT with and without
 690 DVB-S2(x) encoding would be transparent to the IoT terminal, since the time-packing signalling,
 691 NB-IoT regeneration and the DVB-S2(X) encapsulation would be performed at the satellite feeder link.

692 5.2. Future Extensions

693 After presenting the main conclusions, we introduce the possible future research extensions of
 694 this work. Specifically, we consider the following ones: i) Adapt the optical channel to LEO and
 695 MEO scenarios, in order to evaluate the performance of the proposed relaying strategies at different
 696 satellite orbits; ii) Evaluate the benefits of using time-packing with optical feeder link in the reverse
 697 flow of information, from the IoT terminals to the satellite gateway; iii) Study the viability of using
 698 time-packing techniques as a potential physical layer security scheme. In the first case, the aim
 699 would be to assess the benefits that LEO and MEO satellites could reap from the proposed relaying
 700 architectures. For both LEOs and MEOs, the slant range and elevation angle of the feeder link changes
 701 continuously with the time and, as consequence, the optical channel modeling has to be adjusted
 702 accordingly to consider these effects. The complexity of the proposed schemes should be also analyzed
 703 in detail, since LEO and MEO satellites have more energy constraints than GEO ones due to the
 704 Earth/Moon may block the sunlight that reaches their solar panels. In the second case, the reverse
 705 link should be evaluated by replacing the time-packing scheme with a frequency-packing one. It is
 706 well known that NB-IoT uses SC-FDMA in the uplink and, as consequence, solutions that increase
 707 the spectral efficiency by overlapping the subcarriers should be better considered. As side effect,

708 SC-FDMA can compensate in part the increase of PAPR that that overlapping in the time and frequency
 709 domains introduce. Finally, in the third case, the ISI that the process of shrinking the pulses/subcarriers
 710 introduces could be used as an artificial noise signal, which can mask the desired information from
 711 potential eavesdroppers.

712 **Author Contributions:** J. B., and A. D. conceived, designed and analyzed the experiments; J.B. was oriented to
 713 DVB-S2(X) and NB-IoT signalling, time-packing generation and its suppression, A.D. channel modeling, J.B. and
 714 A.D. wrote the paper

715 **Funding:** This research was funded by Agencia Estatal de Investigación (AEI) and the European Regional
 716 Development Fund (FEDER) with grant number TERESA- TEC2017-90093-C3-1-R (AEI/FEDER,UE), and has
 717 been based upon work from COST Action CA19111 NEWFOCUS, supported by COST (European Cooperation in
 718 Science and Technology).

719 **Acknowledgments:** The authors would like to express their own deepest gratitude to Prof. Càndid Rèig for his
 720 support for publishing this paper in this Special Issue.

721 **Conflicts of Interest:** The authors declare that there is no personal circumstances or interest that may be perceived
 722 as inappropriately influencing the representation or interpretation of reported research results. The funders
 723 had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the
 724 manuscript, or in the decision to publish the results.

725 Abbreviations

726 The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

727	BLER	BLOCK Error Rate
	DVB-S2	Digital Video Broadcasting Second Generation Satellite
	DVB-S2X	Digital Video Broadcasting Second Generation Extension
	FSO	Free Space Optical
	GEO	Geostationary Earth Orbit
	HTS	High Throughput Satellites
	IM/DD	Intensity Modulation / Decision Detection
	MCS	Modulation and Coding Scheme
	NOMA	Non Orthogonal Multiple Access
728	NPBCH	Narrowband Physical Broadcast Channel
	NPDCCH	Narrowband Physical Downlink Control Channel
	NPDSCH	Narrowband Physical Downlink Shared Channel
	NPSS	Narrowband Primary Synchronization Signal
	NSSS	Narrowband Secondary Synchronization Signal
	NB-IoT	Narrow-Band Internet of Things
	OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
	OTA	Over-The-Air
	PAM	Pulse Amplitude Modulation
	QPSK	Quadrature Pulse Shift Keying
	THR	Throughput

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Figure 17. End-to-end Block Error Rate (BLER) versus E_b/N_0 in the access link for a NB-IoT frame ($SNR_{\text{feeder}} = 15\text{ dB}$). NB-IoT code rates: 0.2222 (red square), 0.259 (red circle), 0.3 (red diamond), 0.444 (blue square), 0.5319 (blue circle), 0.6 (blue diamond), 0.6386 (magenta square), 0.7678 (magenta circle), 0.8628 (magenta diamond). Solid lines with filled markers: BLER 10^{-2} requirement fulfilled. Dashed-lines with unfilled markers: BLER 10^{-2} requirement not fulfilled. Wind speed: $v = 21\text{ m/s}$; Beam width: $W_0 = 10\text{ cm}$.

Figure 18. End-to-end Block Error Rate (BLER) versus E_b/N_0 in the access link for a NB-IoT frame transmitted through regenerative satellite (decode forward) ($SNR_{\text{feeder}} = 15$ dB). NB-IoT code rates: 0.2222 (red square), 0.259 (red circle), 0.3 (red diamond), 0.444 (blue square), 0.5319 (blue circle), 0.6 (blue diamond), 0.6386 (magenta square), 0.7678 (magenta circle), 0.8628 (magenta diamond). Solid lines with filled markers: BLER 10^{-2} requirement fulfilled. Dashed-lines with unfilled markers: BLER 10^{-2} requirement not fulfilled. Wind speed: $v = 21$ m/s and diameter of aperture's telescope: $W_0 = 10$ cm

Figure 19. End-to-end Block Error Rate (BLER) versus E_b/N_0 in the access link for a NB-IoT frame encapsulated in a DVB-S2(X) satellite frame ($\text{SNR}_{\text{feeder}} = 15 \text{ dB}$). NB-IoT code rates: 1/3 (red), 2/3 (blue), 0.96 (magenta). DVB-S2(X) code rates: 2/3 (squares), 0.8 (circles), 0.9 (diamonds). Solid lines with filled markers: BLER 10^{-2} requirement fulfilled. Dashed-lines with unfilled markers: BLER 10^{-2} requirement not fulfilled. Wind speed: $v = 21 \text{ m/s}$ and diameter of aperture's telescope: $W_0 = 10 \text{ cm}$.